

DISABLED PEOPLE

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Annotation: This article is about disabilities and people with disabilities. Disability is total or temporary loss of working ability due to accident such as illness, injury. Such person have either physical or mental disabilities and they also need social support and protection.

Keywords and expressions: disability, defect, illness, injury, accident.

We have our own values, just as every nation has its own values. One of them is not to discriminate against the elderly in our country and at the same time to help those who are weaker than us despite being young. But today we are all guilty of discriminating against people with disabilities. Disabled people need support from healthy people. Undoubtedly, people with disabilities want to do the same thing that able-bodied people do, like visiting museums restaurants and public places. But reaching this level will not be easy. And they need the support of us healthy people.

Life forms of disabled people

It is worth saying that the life forms of disabled people are more complicated than ours. Life being disabled people has its up and down, but so do other people. Many people have the ability to do what they want when they like. But being disabled can have its limitations. At time they get very frustrated by not being able to do things other people take for granted such as walking unaided or planning a journey. We should ask ourselves these questions :

"How can we show respect to disabled people? "

Why should we help them? "

When we meet people with disabilities in public place, we should treat them without disrespect as we treat healthy people. An individual's disability can play a major role in his or her life whether it's positive or negative. But overcoming the

challenges and developing confidence is vital and admirable. As a society, it is our most duty to allow people with disabilities to experience a life they deserve. Many scientists have expressed their opinion about disabled people and Stephen Hawking also left similar sentences in one of his works: "Disability need not be an obstacle to success"

The result...

It can be seen that our people have a high sense of respect for the elderly and the weak. We cannot find this feeling in other nations.

Conclusion....

It should be conclusion that there are many disabled people in our country. How we treat them defines who we are? It was not for nothing that our ancestors said the phrase "what you see in a bird's nest". Since we are Uzbek people it is customary for uzbeks to always help those who are weaker than us. And I hope that this culture will not change in the future

References:

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